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Abstract: The people of coastal area of Bangladesh are always facing the extreme weather events. Humanitarian lessons of social and religious value plays the vital role to help each other even making one's life endangers. This study was conducted to explore the vulnerability and strength of the community for their resilience in terms of social capital. This study was conducted in a village of Shyamnagar Upazilla of Satkhira District; an Aila affected coastal community of Bangladesh during June 2018-December 2019. VRA protocols were used to collect data. The community people mentioned that their family integrity is breaking down day by day following seasonal migration and livelihood threats. Their value system is also endangers. Village politics, discrimination and losing religious practices are the inevitable result of deteriorating trust. This study revealed that the amity among the community people is somehow good and the Government aid and policy as well as Information services are very favorable to build a resilient community. The investment of national and donors emphasized in relief and the strengthening of institutional capacity but attention in the other human and social attributes which are also much more important for a resilient community should also give priority.

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Introduction

The modern concept of social capital renewed the academic interest in social science: the relationship between trust, social networks and the resilient development of a vulnerable society. Aldrich (2012) found that “participation among networked members; providing information and knowledge to individuals in the group; and creating trustworthiness.” He showed that “higher levels of social capital work together more effectively to guide resources to where they are needed.” Many studies confirm that after disasters, most survivors see social connections and community as critical for their recovery. Researcher found that “higher levels of social capital reduce transaction costs, increase the probability of collective action, and make cooperation among individuals more likely.” Social capital is therefore “an asset, a functioning propensity for mutually beneficial collective action.”

Review of Literature:

Research findings shows that “less resilience fails to mobilize collectively and often must wait for recover guidance and assistance” This implies that vulnerable populations are not solely characterized in terms of age, income, etc., but in terms of “their lack of connections and embeddedness in social networks.” In different words, “the most effective—and perhaps least expensive—way to mitigate disasters is to create stronger bonds between individuals in vulnerable populations.”

Daniel Aldrich (2012) suggested in his case studies that social capital is more important for disaster resilience than physical and financial capital, and more important than conventional explanation.

The people of coastal area of Bangladesh are always facing the extreme weather events. These areas are most vulnerable to climate change due to sea level rise, salinity intrusion, flooding, increased frequency and intensity of cyclone and storm surge, and increased coastal and riverbank erosion. Super cyclone ‘SIDR’ in November 2007 and cyclone ‘AILA’ in May 2009 are the recent examples of extreme events that affected the thousands of people, many of whom are women and children and destroyed livelihood options of millions of coastal people. It is often seen that the government response takes sometimes even a week with insufficient aid and coordination capacities due to the poor transport system. (WASH CLUSTER, 2009) High density of population is another problem for the government to address properly. The period between hit of disaster and institutional response is a crucial time for the people. It has been found in Bangladesh that in this time people helps each other without discrimination poor and rich, racism and any other confliction issues. Humanitarian lessons of social and religious value plays the vital role to help each other even making one’s life endanger. When the river bank become collapsed the community people rush to the spot without waiting for the institutional assistance due the

diving force of humanity. This humanity and values become vulnerable when the institutional assistance comes to the community through political and power channel.

Objective of the study

To know the extent of social capitals that are playing role in building resilient community in the southern coastal area of Bangladesh.

To explore the vulnerability and strength of the community for their resilience in terms of social capital.

Area of study

The area was purposively selected as the selected community faces several climate hazards recently. This study was conducted in the village: Kalinchi, Union: Ramjannagor (Total population 29368, Male-14168, Female-15200) under Shyamnagor Upazilla of Satkhira District; an Aila affected coastal community of Bangladesh.

Materials and methods:

This study was conducted during June 2018-December 2019. The village occupies 5000 people (Male-female ratio is 1.07). (BBS, 2011) who lives in about 1000 houses.

Three FGD were done where 25-30 respondents were selected as a representative of each ten houses of the selected vulnerable community for each FGD. Women and different livelihood groups were considered in the participant selection. The Vulnerability Reduction Assessment (VRA) (Andrew Crane Droesch, 2008) protocols were used to facilitate the FGD. The respondents were requested to put their vote against the variables like family integrity, social values, and trust to each other, amity, and Government policy of aid and information accessibility. The respondents were requested to put values (0-10) against each character according to its severity of vulnerability and future risk. A panel of five members was formed including social elites and leaders to validate the response of the respondents.

Results and discussion:

Family integrity- It was considered as an important variable as the good family relation makes a person more secured than any other options. It was found that most of the respondents said that their strength in family integrity

was medium(5 score out of 10) and vulnerability is increasing day by day.Following the recent cyclone, water surge and saline water intrusion made their crop production system vulnerable and increased their food insecurity that forces them to seasonal migration and shifting of family member to another for livelihood. It also impacts on their joint family system to breakdown.

Value system:

A society becomes more resilient when it occupies strong value system.This ideology defines what is right or wrong and guides ethical behavior based on those beliefs.A person’s values determine his or her character and actions, even in situations where negative consequences might exist for doing the right thing. It was found that the community people mentioned as the vulnerability of the value system was medium and future risk is more than medium. The community people knows the right as right and wrong is as wrong but sometimes it goes out of their grip when the influential power plays role unethically during the distribution of institutional aid support. Continuing ill practice makes the moral strength of a community weak that makes the community vulnerable.

Trust to each other: Trust can be explained as the relationships between people. Conceptually, trust is also the relationships within and between social groups (families, friends, communities, organizations, companies, nations etc.). To frame the dynamics of inter-group and intra-group interactions in terms of trust is popular. Without trust all the contingency plan become paralyzed.

In this study it was found the vulnerability and future risk of trust was increasing. People explained that the people of this area were strong in religious faith; natural resource was abandoned to meet the livelihood and had the social harmony. Following the several natural hazards the stress, anxiety, and unrest and associated many other difficulties made the life of them complex. Village politics, discrimination and loosing religious practices are the inevitable result of deteriorating trust.

Amity: Mutual understanding is very necessary among the neighbors, groups, community for a peaceful sustainable society. It helps the people to help each other during any disaster period. In the ancient period when the people live in group they used to share their food and shelter among themselves for their surviving. This study revealed that the vulnerability of amity among the community people is below the average that means somehow good. The villagers gave example that in the villages there was only one well constructed mosque. When Aila hits there was no place to take shelter but this Mosque. In that time the villagers; Hindus and Muslims all took shelter in the roof of the Mosque without considering any religious constraints.

Government aid and policy: It was found that Government aid and policy was more favorable to the resilient. The community people explained that due to the awareness program, social mobilization of different NGOs and influence of civil society the Government has made the policy resilient livelihood friendly. Government has established different department and ministry to response the disaster quickly. Local Government authority is also sincere regarding this issue. Government has generated policies and formed different committee from national level to community level. Planning, CRA, RRAP financing in DRR is now participatory process with the local community that is why the community people feel more resilient than ever before.

Information services: Communication, network and access to information is very important for the development even in disaster period. Due the lack of early warning system once the people could not know the messages of disaster to take shelter which used to tolls huge lives and properties. Now the people of this community is risk free and feels resilient as they have well established early warning system, trained volunteer, cyclone and flood shelter. Certainly it is a positive impact of the effort of GO-NGOs.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

This study shows that the Government aid and policy as well as Information Services are very favorable to build a resilient community. The investment of national and donors emphasized in relief and the strengthening of institutional

capacity but attention in the other human and social attributes which are also much more important for a resilient community should also give priority. If the social and religious values could be strengthened that energizes the humanity then the situation could be better and resilient of a community and would be irony strengthened. The people of the community who lives in spiritual void get strong social capital. The stronger social capital might serve as informal insurance to overcome the constraints to be more resilient.

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